

MORPHOLOGICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COLLOID SILICA / WATERBORNE POLYURETHANE NANOCOMPOSITE

Hsu-Chiang Kuan and Chen-Chi M. Ma

Department of Chemical Engineering

National Tsing Hua University

HsinChu, Taiwan, 300

SUMMERY : A novel nanocomposite consists of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane has been prepared. Nanocomposites was investigated by Fourier-Transform Infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR) and Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC). The completion of the reaction and the final molecular weight of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites were determined. Si-mapping technique was used to observe the dispersion of silica in the nanocomposite. Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) were used to study the thermal properties and morphology of nano-silica/waterborne polyurethane. Thermal properties show that adding nano-silica would improve the thermal degradation properties by 25 °C . The morphology studies show that nano-silica is well dispersed in waterborne polyurethane matrix within a nano-scale(20nm). Mechanical property tests showed that adding colloid silica would improve the tensile properties (greater than 100%) and wear resistance property.

Key word : colloid silica, waterborne polyurethane, nanocomposite, mechanical properties, morphology

INTRODUCTION

Aqueous (waterborne) polyurethanes (WPU) are high performance polymers as known for their excellent properties, such as abrasion resistance, hardness, flexibility, chemical and solvent resistance, gloss, and low temperature film formation. Water dispersions, lattices or emulsions of polyurethane elastomers or coating permit the application of polyurethanes from an aqueous medium. For waterborne polyurethane systems, only water was evaporated during the drying process, thus rendering these systems

safe with regard to the environment. They are non-toxic, non-flammable and do not generate polluted air or wastewater. [1-5]

With the aim of exploring the so-called “ high-performance” materials, a combination of organic polymers with inorganic materials has been examined. Addition of a filler of ultrafine particle such as silica gel, colloid silica, calcium carbonate, or carbon black to organic polymer has been utilized to prepare composite materials of high strength.[6-18]

This study presents the synthesis of nanocomposites from waterborne polyurethane and colloid silica. Waterborne polyurethane disperses in water solution; consequently, the hydrophilic colloid silica would be dispersed more stably in waterborne polyurethane than in solvent-based polyurethane. Several characterizations and property measurements of nanocomposite were also conducted in this study.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

The 3-isocyanatethyl-3,5,5-trimethyl-cyclohexylisocyanate (IPDI) was purchased from the TCI CO., Tokyo, Japan. Neopentylglycol (NPG), Trimethylolpropane (TMP) and Dimethylol-propionic acid (DMPA) were received from Lancaster Company, Morecambe ,England.. Polycaprolactone (PCL) with molecular weight 550 · 830 · 1000 were obtained from Solvay Interlox Company, Cheshire,U.K. Triethylamine (TEA) and Ethylenediamine (EDA) were supplied by the Tedia Company, Ohio,U.S.A.

2.Synthesis of Colloid Silica / Waterborne Polyurethane Nanocomposite

The 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP) solvent was distilled over P₂O₅ and stored in the presence of 4 Å molecular sieve to keep it dry. A 500-ml round bottom, 4-necked separable glass reactor with a mechanical stirrer, thermometer, and condenser, was used in the preparation of silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites. Reaction was conducted in a N₂ atmosphere at constant temperature. The colloid silica (0,1,2,4 phr (part per hundred resin)) and PCL were mixed and dried in the reactor at 120°C for 1h. A stoichiometric mixture of IPDI, NPG, TMP, DMPA and acetone were fed into the reactor. The NCO-terminated prepolymer was obtained. TEA was added and stirred 30 min for neutralization. Finally, the EDA/H₂O solution was added and carefully controlled by syringe pump. Vacuum evaporator under reducing pressure was used to remove NMP and water, then the silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite was obtained. The product was a stable PU anionomer dispersion with a solid content of about 35%.

3. Characterization and property measurements

3-1 Fourier Transfer Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

FT-IR spectra of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite were recorded between 400-4000 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet Avatar 320 FT-IR spectrometer, Nicolet Instrument Corporation, Madison, WI., U.S.A. The colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite sample was coated on a KBr plate. A minimum of 32 scans was signal averaged with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} within the 400-4000 cm^{-1} range. The characteristic absorption peaks of functional group were detected and monitored during the synthesis reaction such as N-H stretching at 3500 cm^{-1} , O-H stretching at 3300 cm^{-1} , NCO stretching at 2270 cm^{-1} , C=O stretching of urethane at 1740 cm^{-1} , C=O stretching of urea at 1660 cm^{-1} and Si-O asymmetric stretching at 1150 cm^{-1} .

3-2 Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM)

Surface morphology of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite were investigated by Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL JSM 840A, Japan). The fracture surfaces were sputter coated with gold prior to scanning. The distributions of Si atoms in the hybrid creamers were obtained from SEM EDX mapping. The white points in the figures denote the Si atoms.

3-3 Transmission Electronic Microscopy (TEM)

Transmission Electronic Microscope (JEOL-2000FX, Japan) was utilized to investigate the morphology of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite. The samples for TEM study were first prepared by placing the nanocomposite into epoxy capsules and cured at 70°C for 24hr in a vacuum oven. Then the cured epoxies containing colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite were microtomed with Leica Ultra cut into 80-100nm thick slices at -80°C. A carbon layer of 3 nm thick was deposited on these slices that being on 200 mesh copper nets for TEM observation. The type of TEM used is.

3-4 Tensile properties

Colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane film were cut into dumb-bells shape according to the ASTM D683 testing method by Instron testing machine(type: Mini 44). The crosshead speed was 2mm/min. The dimensions of samples were 6.0×5.0×1.4 mm (length×width×thickness). Six specimens were tested in each case. All tests were performed at ambient temperature of 25±2°C.

3-5 Wear properties

A 10cm x10cm film was prepared and then fixed it on wearing machine (type : PT-3050 Taber, Perfect International Instrument., Taiwan) with 1kg load. The weight loss were measured after 500 ·

1000·1500·2000 and 3000 wearing cycles by ASTM D4060-90 method. The wear index I was calculated as : $I = ((W_1 - W_2) / C) \times 1000$, where W_1 is the original weight of sample, W_2 is the weight after wearing, and C is the wearing cycles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Characterization of waterborne polyurethane

The structures of the colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite coatings were analyzed by FT-IR, as indicated in Fig.1 and Table 1. As the reaction completion the N=C=O stretching group of IPDI at 2270 cm^{-1} disappeared completely. The C=O stretching of urea at 1640 cm^{-1} and the C=O stretching of urethane at 1735 cm^{-1} appeared and grew from the second step. The chain extender is DMPA, it has one equivalent -COOH group on one side, the -OH peaks become very broad (3600 cm^{-1} ~2600 cm^{-1}). The Asymmetric stretching peak of Si-O-Si bonding at 1100 cm^{-1} is also clear.

The molecular weight of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane was measured by GPC. Results indicated that the number average molecular weight (M_n) of waterborne polyurethane synthesized herein ranged from 4000 to 12000. PDI (polydispersity index) is ranged from 20. to 3.0.

Figure 1 FT-IR spectrum of colloid silica / IPDI-PCL based poly(urea-urethane) nanocomposite for functional group identification

Table 1 The main IR absorption peaks of colloid silica / IPDI-PCL based poly(urea-urethane) nanocomposite

Functional group	Types of vibration	Wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Strength
-N=C=O	Isocyanate stretch	2275cm ⁻¹	Broad and very strong
-C=O	Urethane stretch	1750~1700 cm ⁻¹	Very strong
-C=O	Urea stretch	1670~1640 cm ⁻¹	Very strong
-C-O	Ether stretch	1310 ~ 1000	Sharp and strong
-O-H	Alcohol stretch	3500~3200 cm ⁻¹	Very broad and very strong
-COO-H	Carboxylic acid stretch	3300 ~ 2500	Broad
-N-H	Amine stretch	1650~1500 cm ⁻¹	Sharp and strong
-C-H	Hydrocarbon stretch	3000~2800 cm ⁻¹	Sharp and medium
Si-O-Si	Asymmetric stretch	1000~1200 cm ⁻¹	strong

2. Morphological Properties

Figure 2(a) showed the SEM microphotograph and the EDX Si-mapping of colloid silica/waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites. Those figures presented that the colloid silica was well dispersed in WPU matrix. Figure 2(b) showed the TEM of cross sectional views of colloid silica/waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites, the aggregation size of colloid silica in waterborne polyurethane matrix was around 100nm, and the particle size of colloid silica was about 20nm.

Figure 2(a) The SEM Microphotograph and Si-mapping of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite

Figure 2 (b) Transmission electron micrographs of the Silica / Waterborne Polyurethane Nanocomposite

3. Thermal properties

Figure 3 presents the 10% weight loss temperatures of colloid silica/waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites (molecular weight of soft segment was 830) with 0,1,2,4,8 and 16 phr silica contents were 247.5, 272.5, 270.7, 260.3 and 268.6°C, respectively. Results indicated that adding colloid silica increased the temperature of thermal degradation, however, it may reduce the molecule weight of

waterborne polyurethane. These two effects competed each other. Consequently, the thermal degradation temperature increased initially and then dropped. The thermal degradation temperature of the nanocomposite with 1 phr colloid silica was the highest(272.5°C).

Figure 3 Thermal degradation temperature of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite with different silica content

4. Mechanical Properties

4-1 Tensile Properties

Table 2 summarizes the tensile properties of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite. Adding colloid silica to the waterborne polyurethane will increase the initial tensile modulus of the composites.. The tensile modulus of the colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite with 4phr silica increased from 20.2MPa to 40.8Mpa (101.9%). The colloid silica plays an important role in strengthening the composites by effectively transferring the stress between the silica and the polyurethane matrix.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane (soft segment molecular weight 1250) nanocomposite with different clay contents

Silica contents (phr)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Max stress (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
0	20.2	3.97	210
1	29.5	4.34	57.2
2	32.1	4.95	58.7
4	35.9	6.23	54.6
8	40.8	7.61	44.7

4-2 Wear Resistance

In the abrasion test, the wear index of colloid silica/waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites was conducted when the silica content was 0,2,4,8 phr. From Figure 4, the results showed that adding small amount colloid silica would increase the wear resistance of nanocomposite efficiently, for example, when 2phr colloid silica was added, wear index become 25% of neat waterborne polyurethane.

Figure 4 The Abrasion Test of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite

CONCLUSIONS

Colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposites have been synthesized successfully. FT-IR and GPC have been used to characterize the nanocomposite. SEM microphotographs and Si-mapping of Colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite indicated that colloid silica was well dispersed in waterborne polyurethane. TEM microphotographs revealed that the size of colloid silica remained in waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite was about 100nm, that is, nano-dispersed in nanocomposites. Thermal properties of the nanocomposite measured by TGA indicated that adding colloid silica increased the temperature of thermal degradation by 21°C. Mechanic property tests showed that adding colloid silica would improve the tensile properties (tensile modulus increased by 101.9% when colloid silica content was 8phr) and wear properties of colloid silica / waterborne polyurethane nanocomposite (wear index wear index become 25% of neat waterborne polyurethane when silica content was 2 phr)

REFERENCES

1. Michael J. Dvorchak, Using “High Performance Two-Component Waterborne Polyurethane” Wood Coatings, *Journal of Coating Technology*, **69**(886), 47(1997)
2. B.Vogt-Brinbrich “Novel synthesis of low VOC polymeric dispersions and application in waterborne coatings” *Progress in Organic Coatings* 29 (1996) 31-38
3. Volker Duecoffre, Wolfgang Diener, Carmen Flosbach, Walter Schubert “Emulsifiers with high chemical resistance : A key to high performance waterborne coatings” *Progress in Organic Coatings* 34 (1998) 200-205
4. Chien-Hsin Yang, Huey-Jia Yang, Ten-Chin Wen, Ming-Sieng Wu, Jian-Sheng Chang “Mixture design approaches to IPDI-H₆XDI-XDI ternary diisocyanate-base waterborne polyurethanes” *Polymer* 40 (1999) 871-885
5. J.Huybrechts, P.Bruylants, A.Vaes, A.De Marre “Surfactant-free emulsion for waterborne two-component polyurethane coatings” *Progress in Organic Coatings* 38 (2000) 67-77
6. Jose Sepulcre—gullabert, Teresa P. Ferrandz-Gomez and Jose Miguel Martin-Martinez, “Properties of polyurethane adhesives contining natural calcium + fumed silica mixtures”, *J.Adhesion Sci. Technol*, Vol 15, No.2,187-203(2001)
7. Ana M. Torro-Palau, Juan C. Fernandez-Garcia and A. Cesar Orgiles-Barcelo, “Rheological Properties of polyurethane adhesives containing Silica as filler: Influence of the nature and surface chemistry of silica”, *Macromol. Symp.*, 169, 191-196(2001)
8. Jose Sepulcre-Guilaert, Teresa del Pilar Ferrandiz-Gomez and Jose Miguel Martin-Martinez, “Use of

- calcium carbonate- fumed silica Mixtures as filler in polyurethane adhesives”, *Macromol. Symp.*,169,185-190(2001)
9. Katsuki Kusakabe, Seiki Yoneshige and Shigeharu Morooka, “Seperationof benzene/cyclohexane mixtures using polyurethane-silica hybride membranes”, *Journal of Membrane Science.*, 149,29-37(1998)
 10. Hideki Goda and Curtis W.Frank, “Fluorescence studies of the hybride composite of Segmented-polyurethane and silica”,*Chem. Mater.*,13,2783-2787(2001)
 11. Ana M. Torro-Palau, Juan C. Fernandez-Garcia, A. Cesar Orgiles-Barcelo and Jose M. Martin-Martinez,”Characterization of polyurethane containing different silicas”,*International Journal of Adhesion & Adhesives*,21,1-9(2001)
 12. T.Branyik, G.Kuncova and J. Paca, “The use of silica gel prepared by sol-gel method and polyurethane foam as microbial carriers in the continuous degradation of phenol”, *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*,54,168-172(2000)
 13. R.C.R. Nunes, R.A. Pereira ,J.L.C. Fonseca and M. R. Pereira, ”X-ray studies on compositions of polyurethane and silica”, *Polymer testing*, 20,707-712(2001)
 14. Tae-Jin Yim,Sun Young Kim and Ki-Pung Yoo,”Fabrication and Thermophysical Characterization of Nano-Porous Silica-Polyurethane Hybrid Aerogel by Sol-Gel Processing and Supercritical Solvent Drying Technique”,*Korean J. Chem. Eng.*,19.159-166(2002)
 15. Zoran S. Petrovic, Ivan Javni, Alan Waddon and Gyorgy Banhehegyi,”Structure and Properties of polyurethane-Silica Nanocomposites”, *Journal of Applied polymer Science.*,133-151(1999)
 16. No-Hyung Park, Joon-Woo lee and Kyung-Do Suh,”In situ polyurethane /Silica Composite Formation Via a Sol-Gel Process”, *Journal of Applied polymer Science*, Vol. 84,2327-2334(2002)
 17. In-Seok Oh. No-Hyung Park and Kyung-Do Suh,”Mechanical and Surface Hardness Properties of Ultraviolet-Cured Polyurethane Acrylate Anionomer /Silica”, *Journal of Applied polymer Science*,75,968-975(2000)
 18. Jianye Wen and James E. Mark, “Sol-Gel Preparation of Composites of poly(dimethylsiloxane) with SiO₂/TiO₂ ,and Their Mechanical properties”, *Polymer Journal*,Vol. 27, No.5,492-502(1995)